

Ec-CLS-modules

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Abstract.

In this not we consider generalization of the notion of y -closed submodule and CLS-module called y -ec-closed submodule and an Ec-CLS-module respectively. And we study the properties of this kind of module. Also we study the direct sum of an Ec-CLS-module.

Keywords: y -closed submodule; Extending and CLS-modules.

Introduction:

Throughout this paper R will be a commutative ring with identity, and all modules will be unitary left R -modules. A proper submodule N of an R -module M is called an essential submodule in M , if for every nonzero submodule K of M has nonzero intersection with N [1]. A submodule N of M is called closed in M , if it has no proper essential extension in M [1]. A submodule N is called ec-closed submodule if N contains essentially a cyclic submodule, i.e. there exists $n \in N$ such that $\langle n \rangle \subseteq_e N$ [2]. A submodule N is called y -closed submodule of a module M , if $\frac{M}{N}$ is nonsingular [1]. An R -module M is called anc (CS-module), if every submodule of M is essential in a direct summand of M . A Tercan introduced the following concept: An R -module M is called a CLS-module, if every y -closed submodule of M is a direct summand of M [3].

In this paper, we introduce the concept of y -ec-closed submodule of a module M , and we defined a CLS-module that every y -ec-closed submodule is a direct summand.

In section one, we defined y -ec-closed submodules and give some properties of these submodules.

In section two, we give the definition of Ec-CLS-module, we also give their properties. We prove that any direct summand of an Ec-CLS-module is an Ec-CLS-module.

In section three, we study the direct sum of an Ec-CLS-module. It is shown that if $M = M_1 \oplus M_2$, where M_1 and M_2 are an Ec-CLS-modules such that $\text{ann}M_1 + \text{ann}M_2 = R$, then M is an Ec-CLS-module.

1. y -ec-closed submodule.

Definition (1.1): Let N be an ec-submodule of M , N is called y -ec-closed submodule of M , if $\frac{M}{N}$ is nonsingular.

Remarks and examples (1.2):

1. For any uniform R -module M is y -ec-closed submodule of M .

- The module Z as Z -module contains only $\langle 0 \rangle$ and \bar{Z} which are y -ec-closed submodules of Z .
- Every y -ec-closed submodule of M is y -closed submodule.
- Every y -ec-closed submodule of M is ec-closed submodule of M and, then it is closed. The converse is not true, for example; $M = Z_6$ as Z -module and $\{\bar{0}, \bar{2}, \bar{4}\}$ is ec-closed (closed) submodule of Z_6 , but $\frac{Z_6}{\{\bar{0}, \bar{2}, \bar{4}\}} = \{\bar{0}, \bar{3}\}$ is not y -ec-closed.

Proposition (1.3): Let M be a nonsingular R -module, and let N be an ec-submodule of M . Then N is y -ec-closed in M , if and only if N is ec-closed submodule.

Proof: The necessity is given by Remark 1.2(4). Conversely, suppose that M is nonsingular R -module, and N is ec-closed submodule of M . If $Z(\frac{M}{N}) = \frac{A}{N}$, where A is a submodule of M with $N \subseteq A$. Hence $N \subseteq_e A$ by [1, prop.1.21, p.32], but N is ec-closed, then N is closed. Therefore, $N = A$ and there exists $n \in N$ such that $nR \subseteq_e N$. Thus $Z(\frac{M}{N}) = 0$, and hence N is y -ec-closed submodule of M .

Examples (1.4):

- Every nonsingular simple R -module M is y -ec-closed of M .
- Every nonsingular uniform R -module M has only two y -ec-closed submodule $\langle 0 \rangle$ and M .

Remark (1.5): Let R be an integral domain and let N be an ec-submodule of R -module M . If $\frac{M}{N}$ is torsion free, then N is y -ec-closed of M .

Proof: Since R is an integral domain and $\frac{M}{N}$ is torsion free, then $0 = T(\frac{M}{N}) = Z(\frac{M}{N})$ by

[1, p.31]. Then $\frac{M}{N}$ is nonsingular and hence N is an y -ec-closed submodule.

Proposition (1.6): Let M be an R -module and A, B be ec-submodule of M such that $A \subseteq B$ then:

- If A is an y -ec-closed of M , then A is an y -ec-closed of B .
- If $\frac{B}{A}$ is y -ec-closed of $\frac{M}{A}$, then B is y -ec-closed submodule of M .
- If A is y -ec-closed of M , then $\frac{M}{B}$ is singular if and only if $B \subseteq_e M$.
- If A is y -ec-closed in B , and B is y -ec-closed of M , then A is y -ec-closed submodule of M .

Proof:

1. It is clear.

2. Let $\frac{B}{A}$ be y -ec-closed of $\frac{M}{A}$, then there exists $\frac{\langle x \rangle}{A} \subseteq_e \frac{B}{A}$, where $x \in B$ and $\frac{A}{B}$ is nonsingular. But $\frac{A}{B} \cong \frac{M}{B}$ by third isomorphism theorem), then B is y -closed and since $\langle x \rangle \subseteq_e B$, thus B is y -ec-closed of M . By the same we can prove the converse.

3. By Remark 1.2(3) and [4, prop.2.1.18, p.27].

4. It is clear by Remark 1.2(4) and [4, prop.2.1.10, p.24].

Proposition (1.7): Let M be an R -module and A, B be an ec-submodules of M , then A is y -ec-closed submodule of $A+B$ if and only if $A \cap B$ is y -ec-closed submodule of B .

Proof: Assume that A is y -ec-closed submodule of $A+B$, then A is y -closed submodule of $A+B$ by Remark 1.2(3). Therefore $A \cap B$ is y -closed of B , by [4, prop.2.16, p.22]. But A is y -ec-closed, then there exists $x \in A$ such that $\langle x \rangle \subseteq_e A$, $\langle x \rangle \cap (A \cap B) \subseteq_e A \cap B$. Hence $A \cap B$ is y -ec-closed submodule of B . The converse by the same way.

Proposition (1.8): Let $M = A \oplus B$ be an R -module, if A is a y -ec-closed submodule of M , then B is nonsingular

Proof: Assume that A is y -ec-closed of M , then A is y -closed submodule of M by Remark 1.2(3). Therefore B is nonsingular by [4, prop.2.1.7].

Proposition (1.9): Let A and B are y -ec-closed submodule of an R -module M , then $A \cap B$ is y -ec-closed of M .

Proof: Since A and B are y -ec-closed, then A and B are y -closed by Remark 1.2(3), then $A \cap B$ is y -closed by [4, prop.2.1.8]. But A and B are y -ec-closed, then there exists $a \in A$ and $b \in B$ such that $\langle a \rangle \subseteq_e A$ and $\langle b \rangle \subseteq_e B$, then $\langle a \rangle \cap \langle b \rangle \subseteq_e A \cap B$ by [1, prop.1.1, p.16]. Hence $A \cap B$ is y -ec-closed of M .

Proposition (1.10): Let M be an R -module, and let $\{B_\alpha | \alpha \in \xi\}$ be an independent family of submodules of M . If $\{A_\alpha | \alpha \in \xi\}$ is a family of submodules of M such that $A_\alpha \subseteq B_\alpha, \forall \alpha \in \xi$, then $\bigoplus A_\alpha$ is y -ec-closed submodule of $\bigoplus B_\alpha, \alpha \in \xi$ if and only if A_α is y -ec-closed submodule of $B_\alpha, \forall \alpha \in \xi$.

Proof: \rightarrow by Remark 1.2(3) and [prop.2.1.20, p.24], we get if $\bigoplus A_\alpha$ is y -ec-closed submodule of $\bigoplus B_\alpha, \alpha \in \xi$ then A_α is y -ec-closed submodule of $B_\alpha, \forall \alpha \in \xi$. Since $\bigoplus A_\alpha$ is y -ec-closed, then there exists $a_\alpha \in A_\alpha, \forall \alpha \in \xi$, such that $\bigoplus \langle a_\alpha \rangle \subseteq_e \bigoplus A_\alpha, \forall \alpha \in \xi$ then $\langle a_\alpha \rangle \subseteq_e A_\alpha, \forall \alpha \in \xi$ by [1, prop.1.10]. Hence A_α is y -ec-closed of B_α .

Conversely, let A_α be y -ec-closed of $B_\alpha, \forall \alpha \in \xi$, then A_α is y -ec-closed submodule of $B_\alpha, \forall \alpha \in \xi$ by Remark 1.2(3), then $\bigoplus A_\alpha$ is y -ec-closed submodule of $\bigoplus B_\alpha, \alpha \in \xi$ by [4, prop.2.1.20, p.29]. Since A_α is y -ec-closed submodule of B_α , then there exists $a_\alpha \in A_\alpha, \forall \alpha \in \xi$ such that $\langle a_\alpha \rangle \subseteq_e A_\alpha, \forall \alpha \in \xi$ then $\bigoplus \langle a_\alpha \rangle \subseteq_e \bigoplus A_\alpha, \forall \alpha \in \xi$ by (prop.1.1(d), p.16), then $\bigoplus A_\alpha$ is y -ec-closed submodule of $\bigoplus B_\alpha, \alpha \in \xi$.

Proposition (1.12): Let M be an R -module and N be y -ec-closed submodule of M , then $[N:M]$ is y -ec-closed ideal of R .

Proof: Let N be an y -ec-closed submodule of M , then N is y -closed of M by Remark 1.2(3). Thus, $[N:M]$ is y -closed ideal of R by [, prop.2.1.21, p.30]. Since N is y -ec-closed submodule of M , then there exists $n \in N$ such that $\langle n \rangle \subseteq_e N, [\langle n \rangle : \langle x \rangle] \subseteq_e [N:M], \forall x \in M$ by [5, prop.3.13, p.59]. Hence $[N:M]$ is y -ec-closed of R .

2. EC-CLS- module:

In this section we introduce the concept of EC-CLS-module and discuss some of basic properties of these modules.

Definition (2.1): An R -module M is called EC-CLS-module, if every y -ec-closed submodule of M is a direct summand of M .

Remark (2.2): Every CLS-module is EC-CLS-module.

Proof: Let M be an R -module, and let A be y -ec-closed submodule of M . Then A is y -closed submodule of M by Remark 1.2(3). But M is CLS-module, then A is a direct summand of M . Therefore M is EC-CLS-module.

Remarks and Examples (2.3):

1. Z as Z -module is EC-CLS-module.
2. It is clear that Z_6 as Z_6 -module is EC-CLS-module.
3. Every singular R -module is EC-CLS-module.
4. Every CS-module is EC-CLS-module, but the converse is not true in general. For example, consider the module $M = Z_8 \oplus Z_2$ as Z -module. Since Z_8 and Z_2 are singular, then M is singular by [1, prop.1.22, p.32] and hence M is CLS-module. Therefore M is EC-CLS-module by Remark 2.2. But M is not CS-module by [6, p.56].
5. Every nonsingular finite uniform dimension, then M is EC-CLS- R -module if R is CS-module.

Proof: Let A be any maximal uniform submodule of M, clearly A is an ec-closed submodule in M. But M is nonsingular, then A is y-ec-closed of M. Since M is EC-CLS-module, then A is a direct summand of M. Hence M is CS. The converse is clear by the above Remark

Lemma (2.4): Any direct summand of an EC-CLS-module is an EC-CLS-module.

Proof: Let $M = A \oplus B$ be an EC-CLS-module. To show that A is EC-CLS-module, let K be an y-ec-closed submodule of A. By third and second isomorphism theorems, we have $\frac{M}{K \oplus B} = \frac{A \oplus B}{K \oplus B} \cong \frac{\frac{A \oplus B}{B}}{\frac{K \oplus B}{B}} \cong \frac{\frac{A}{A \cap B}}{\frac{K}{K \cap B}} = \frac{A}{K}$. Since K is y-ec-closed of A, then $\frac{A}{K}$ is nonsingular. Thus, $K \oplus B$ is an y-ec-closed submodule of M. But M is EC-CLS-module, therefore $K \oplus B$ is a direct summand of M. So, $M = K \oplus B \oplus D$ for some D a submodule of M. Since K is a direct summand of M and $K \subseteq A$, then K is a direct summand of A.

Proposition (2.5): Every y-ec-closed of an EC-CLS-module is an EC-CLS-module.

Proof: Let M be an EC-CLS-module, and N be y-ec-closed submodule of M. Let A be y-ec-closed submodule of N. Then by prop.1.5(4), A is y-ec-closed submodule of M. But M is an EC-CLS-module, therefore A is a direct summand of M. Hence A is a direct summand of N.

Proposition (2.6): Let A and B be submodules of an R-module M, if B is EC-CLS-module and A is an y-ec-closed submodule of M, then $A \cap B$ is a direct summand of B.

Proof: Assume that A is y-ec-closed of M, and B is EC-CLS-module. By the second isomorphism theorem $\frac{A}{A \cap B} \cong \frac{A+B}{B}$. Since $\frac{A+B}{A} \subseteq \frac{M}{A}$, then $\frac{A+B}{A}$ is nonsingular, and hence $A \cap B$ is y-ec-closed submodule of B. But B is EC-CLS-module, therefore $A \cap B$ is a direct summand of B.

Proposition (2.7): Let A be a submodule of an R-module M, if M is an EC-CLS-module, then $\frac{M}{A}$ is an EC-CLS-module.

Proof: Let $\frac{B}{A}$ be an y-ec-closed submodule of $\frac{M}{A}$, then by prop.1.5(2) B is y-ec-closed submodule of M. But M is EC-CLS-module, then B is a direct summand of M. Thus $M = B \oplus K$, for some submodule K of M. Since $A \subseteq B$, then $\frac{M}{A} = \frac{B}{A} \oplus \frac{K+A}{A}$, thus $\frac{M}{A}$ is EC-CLS-module.

3. The direct sums of EC-CLS-modules.

A direct sum of EC-CLS-modules need not EC-CLS-module in general. Hence, we look for conditions under which this property is valid.

Example (3.1): Each of Z_2 and Z_8 are EC-CLS-modules, but $M = Z_2 \oplus Z_8$ is not EC-CLS-module.

Theorem (3.2): Let $M = M_1 \oplus M_2$ be an R-module such that M_1 is M_2 -injective, where M_1 and M_2 are EC-CLS-modules, then M is an EC-CLS-module.

Proof: Let A be an y-ec-closed submodule of M, then $\frac{M}{A}$ is nonsingular. By the second isomorphism theorem $\frac{M_1}{A \cap M_1} \cong \frac{M_1+A}{A} \subseteq \frac{M}{A}$. So, $A \cap M_1$ is an y-ec-closed submodule of M_1 . But M_1 is EC-CLS-module, therefore $A \cap M_1$ is a direct summand of M_1 . Hence $A \cap M_1$ is a direct summand of M. It follows that $A \cap M_1$ is a direct summand of A, then $A = (A \cap M_1) \oplus K$, for submodule K of A. Let $\pi_i: M \rightarrow M_i, i=1,2$ be the projective maps. Now, consider the following diagram.

Where $\alpha = \pi_2|_K$ and $\beta = \pi_1|_K$. Since α is a monomorphism and M_1 is M_2 -injective, then there exists a homomorphism $\varphi: M_2 \rightarrow M_1$ such that $\varphi \circ \alpha = \beta$. Let $L = \{x + \varphi(x) : x \in M_2\}$. One can easily check that L is a submodule of M and $L \cong M_2$. Moreover, $M = M_1 \oplus L$. To show that, let $x \in M = M_1 \oplus M_2$, then $x = m_1 + m_2$, where $m_1 \in M_1$ and $m_2 \in M_2$. Thus $x = m_1 + m_2 + \varphi(m_2) - \varphi(m_2) = (m_1 - \varphi(m_2)) + ((m_2 + \varphi(m_2))) \in M_1 + L$. Now, let $x \in M_1 + L$. Since $x \in L$, then $x = y + \varphi(y)$, $y \in M_2$, thus $y \in M_1 \cap M_2 = 0$ and then $x = 0$. Now, let $k \in K$, then $k = m_1 + m_2$, for some, $m_1 \in M_1$ and $m_2 \in M_2$. Then $m_1 = \beta(k) = \varphi \circ \alpha(k) = \varphi(m_2)$. This implies that $k = m_2 + \varphi(m_2) \in L$. Thus $k \subseteq L$. Since $\frac{M}{A} = \frac{M_1 \oplus L}{(A \cap M_1) \oplus K} \cong \frac{M_1}{(A \cap M_1)} \oplus \frac{L}{K}$, then $\frac{L}{K}$ is nonsingular, and K is an y -ec-closed submodule of L . But $L \cong M_2$ and M_2 is EC-CLS-module, then K is a summand of L . Thus $L = K \oplus D$, for some submodule D of L . Now, since $A \cap M_1$ is a direct summand of M_1 , then $M_1 = (A \cap M_1) \oplus B$, for some B of M_1 . So, $M = M_1 \oplus L = (A \cap M_1) \oplus B \oplus K \oplus D = A \oplus B \oplus D$, then A is a direct summand of M . Hence M is EC-CLS-module.

Proposition (3.3): Let R be a ring and M be an R -module such that $M = \bigoplus M_i$, ($i=1, \dots, n$) is finite direct sum of relatively modules M_i , ($i=1, \dots, n$). Then M is EC-CLS-module if and only if M_i is an EC-CLS-module for each ($i=1, \dots, n$).

Proposition (3.4): Let M_1 and M_2 be EC-CLS-modules such that $\text{ann}M_1 + \text{ann}M_2 = R$, then $M = M_1 \oplus M_2$ is EC-CLS-module.

Proof: Let A be an y -ec-closed submodule of $M_1 \oplus M_2$. Since $\text{ann}M_1 + \text{ann}M_2 = R$, then by the same way of the prove [7, prop.2.2, ch.2], $A = C \oplus D$, where C is a submodule of M_1 and D is a submodule of M_2 . Since $A = C \oplus D$ is y -ec-closed submodule of $M = M_1 \oplus M_2$, then C is y -ec-closed submodule of M_1 and D is y -ec-closed submodule of M_2 by prop.1.11. But M_1 and M_2 are EC-CLS-modules, then C is summand of M_1 and D is a summand of M_2 . So, $A = C \oplus D$ is a summand of $M = M_1 \oplus M_2$. Hence M is an EC-CLS-module.

Proposition (3.5): Let $M = \bigoplus M_i$, ($i=1, \dots, n$) be an R -module such that every y -ec-closed submodule of M is fully invariant, then M is an EC-CLS-module if and only if M_i is EC-CLS-module, ($i=1, \dots, n$).

Proof: \rightarrow Clear by lemma 2.4.

\leftarrow Let A be an y -ec-closed submodule of M . For each ($i=1, \dots, n$), let $\pi_i: M \rightarrow M_i$, be the projection map. Now, let $x \in A$, then $x = \sum_{i=1}^n m_i$, $m_i \in M_i$ and $m_i = 0$, for all except a finite of $i = 1, \dots, n$. Clearly that $\pi_i(x) = m_i \forall i \in I$. Since A is y -ec-closed submodule then by our assumption A is fully invariant and hence $\pi_i(x) = m_i \in A \cap M_i$. So, $x \in \bigoplus (A \cap M_i)$, thus $A \subseteq \bigoplus (A \cap M_i)$. But $\bigoplus (A \cap M_i) \subseteq A$, then $\bigoplus (A \cap M_i) = A$, since A is y -ec-closed submodule of M , therefore $(A \cap M_i)$ is y -ec-closed submodule of M_i , $\forall i$, ($i=1, \dots, n$), by prop.1.8. But M_i is EC-CLS-module $\forall i$, ($i=1, \dots, n$), then $(A \cap M_i)$ is a direct summand of M_i . Thus, A is a direct summand of M .

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